

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE AREA OF MINGBULOQ KIPCHOK LANGUAGES

Usmanov Musurmon is the son of Mamirali

Teacher of the Department of Uzbek
Linguistics of Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13847592>

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Namangan viloyati Mingbuloq qipchoq shevalari areali hamda undagi sheva guruhlarining fonetik-fonologik, leksik va grammatik sathidagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlar haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Areal lingvistika, lingvistik geografiya, sheva, lahja, dialekt, sheva areallari, qipchoq lahjasi.

Abstract: This article discusses the area of Mingbulok Kipchak dialects of Namangan region and the phonetic-phonological, lexical, and grammatical features of the dialect groups in it.

Key words: Areal linguistics, linguistic geography, dialect, dialect, dialect, dialect areas, Kipchak dialect.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается ареал минбулок-кипчакских диалектов Наманганской области и фонетико-фонологические, лексические и грамматические особенности диалектных групп в нем.

Ключевые слова: Ареал языкознания, лингвогеография, диалект, говор, говор, диалектные ареалы, кипчакский диалект.

At the phonetic-phonological, lexical and grammatical level of the Mingbulok Kipchak dialect groups of the Namangan region, there are signs and characteristics that are unique to the Kipchak dialects.

Regional Kipchak-type dialects and branches both have 8 vowels and differ from the central core urban dialects in terms of quantity and quality. [13. 3-14].

It should be mentioned here that it is in Turkic languages "y" and "j" long-standing "which is primary?" We have not yet come to a clear solution to the question, we have not found a clear stop, a historical-linguistic basis. Opinions about this issue, scientific articles dedicated to clarifying and illuminating it to a certain extent, special works on the phonetic structure of Turkic languages were carried out, various scientific and historical views were announced, but they did not give clear and clear conclusions. [5. 61-70].

In the area of Mingbulok Kipchak dialects, the scope of the j affricate is not the same. In the Nayman, Chordona, Momokhan, Qalgandaryo, Beshserka, Nayman, Qairaghochovul, Ingichka, Qirqchek, Madyorovul dialects of the area, j is used instead of y at the beginning of the word. The inhabitants of these large villages mainly live on the left bank of the Syrdarya stream [15.27]. We based them on the views that the consonant y and the affricate j are one of the decisive signs in elucidating the linguistic aspects of the Mingbulok Kipchak dialects [13.5].

1. "Y"lovchi qipchoq shevalari: the number of phonemes is 8: **a, o, i, e, u, ü, ö, o'**; and the amount of phoneme variants is twelve or more: **a, ä, ɔ, o, i, ī, ī, ü, u, ö, o', e.**

The following linguistic features are observed in the speech of the inhabitants of the Sheva area:

a) the law of synharmonism is in effect, and the harmony of the palate is fully preserved: bālīq (baliq), taxta (taxta), toxta (to'xta), didi (dedi), nūmāvā (nega), nūmāñā (nimaga), tāmāñā (tomonga); depending on the hardness of the vowels in the stem, the vowels in the suffix also harmonize: [bāllār] bolalar, [ātāmdī] otamning//otamni; [qāyān] qolgan, [bāryān] borgan, [ičkān] ichgan, [bārdīlār] bordilar, [ākāsī] akasi like.

b) nasalization is followed: bāriñ (boring), keñ (keling), añ (oling), tilpāniñ (telefon qiling) like.

d) between words o' (vö/öv-w) tarzida (sandhi) sandxi is diphthongized: he^wölā (ha, o'la), ö^wv (o'taver), sö^wdīsijir (sog'in sigir), ö^wvr (o'taver), ā^wö^w (olvoraver) like.

e) In this dialect, the vowel sound i is more widely used: äjtīñ (ayting), kīriñ (kiring), böldiñizmi? (bo'ldingizmi?) like always keeps its language back position.

- [a>ä] phenomenon is observed: täšlājdī, šāimājdī like.

- the phenomenon of alternating use of consonants is wider: [p>v]: čāv (chop), tāv (top), jāvīp (yopib), tevā (tepa); [g'>g]: bājāyī (boyagi), āyān (olgan); [g'>v]: bāvlā (nazoratni kuchaytir), sāv (sog'), tāv (tog'), āvđī (og'zi), suvār (sug'or) like.

In the processes of the use of morphological forms in the "y" network of the Kipchak dialect area of Mingbulok district, there are also aspects that are different from the Uzbek literary language and other Uzbek dialects:

Plural (son) -lar of the suffix -nār, -nār-, lār options are used: qīđ+lār (qizlar), bāllār (bolalar); ken+nār (kelinglar), ānnār (olinglar), chīqīnnār (chiqinglar) like.

Tushum and the accusative suffix are indistinguishable, as they are in all Uzbek dialects: [-i//-in//in//dī] is not available in general: qol+i+nī juv+dī (qo'lini yuvdi), bel+i+nī bāj+lā+dī (belini boyladi), bel+iñ+dī baj+lā (belingni bog'la), kōz+i+nī āš+tī (ko'zini ochdi), kōđ+iñ+dī āč (ko'zingni och) like.

Shipment agreement -ga [-yā//yā//kā] used in the form: nūmāv+yā (nega), nūmāñ+yā (nima maqsadda), sij+nī+sī+nī+kā (singlisinikiga) like.

Exit Agreement -dan, in accordance with the syntagmatics of consonants, instead [-tān, -tān] option is used: bār+mās+tān qojdī (bormay qo'ydi), qī+mās+tān ajtmā (bajarib bo'lgandan keyin ayt)like.

Ānā, mānā to demonstrative pronouns šū, bū when pronouns are added: ānā+šī, a:šī (ana shu), mā+šī, mānāv, (mana shu) is used in the style

So'roq olmoshlaridan [nima] pronoun nūmāv is used in the style.

The past tense of the verb [-i)b edī] shaped [-i)b] the adverbial suffix [-i)p] is used: ket+iñ+tī (gone), like bārü:dīm. This situation is also found in Jizzakh: Farish, Khorezm (Kipch.) dialects.

The area of "Y"-speaking Kipchak dialects is Dovduk, Terak, Koshqishloq, Sho'rsuv, Domsa, Karayontoq, Etak, Ozakhlar, Baland Gurtepa, Gurtepa, Ortakishloq, Mulkabad, Uzuntepa, Qairaghochovul in Mingbulok district. The dialect of the inhabitants of such large villages as Kumqishloq, New Life (Attang), Yangabad was introduced.

It should be noted that the linguistic (phonetic-phonological, lexical-semantic and grammatical) characters and characteristics of the speech of the residents of the "y" and "j" network of the Mingbulok Kipchak dialects are similar to those of all Kipchak dialects in Uzbekistan.

In particular, South Khorezm [1.74-82] western dialects of Samarkand region (Nayman, Gallaorol) [7.73], Upper Kashkadarya Kipchak type dialects [1.74-82], southern Aralboi dialects [8.54], South Kazakhstan [10.14] and features characteristic of the Karakalpak, Kazakh languages and many other Uzbek Kipchak dialects are fully observed in the Mingbulok dialect area.

Also, N.A. Baskakov states that the diphthongization of vowels [e, ö, o] at the beginning of the word is a unique feature that distinguishes the Kipchak-Karakalpak language from other Turkic languages [4.28]. This phenomenon also exists in Komik, Gagauz, Karachay-Balkar languages [15.37].

The [i] sound used in Uzbek dialects related to the Kipchak dialect is not lippered, the language has a back vowel, and it is found in all Turkic languages. In the dialect of the residents of the "y" network of the Mingbulok Kipchak area, especially in the settlements of Okhrazal, Baland Gurtepa, Gurtepa, Ortakishloq, Mulkabad, Uzuntepa: ajtīñ, kelīñ, böldīñizmi like The sound [i] does not always keep its position at the back of the tongue. This phoneme is pronounced with a tendency to sound [i] when accompanied by the sounds [y, sh, ch, dj]: bühchäjip (bukchayib); jil (yil), jilādī (yig'ladi); čirāyīm (chirog'im), šiprīndī (supirindi), žilmājip (jilmayib) like.

In the area of Sheva, later and now in the Dashti Kipchak language areas, with the representatives of the Turkic ethnic component language, who were formed as a result of ethnogenetic assimilation (mixing) over a period of more than a century, the Persian-Tajik speaking peoples formed as a result of the migration of representatives of the Turkic ethnic urban and rural population and vibration phenomena have already formed. Researchers have noted such a process as a necessary social condition of the coexistence of ethnically different Persian-Tajik-speaking peoples (in particular, Sogdians, Tajiks, Iranians) and Turkic-speaking ethnic groups in the regions. By modern times, the inhabitants of this area spoke two languages (Persian-Tajik and Turkish). Later, as a result of the migration of many Turkic-speaking ethnic groups to this area, the status of the Turkic ethnic group increased in this area, and as a result, Turkicization of the language of the population increased [2.183-200].

2. "J" Kipchak dialects: "j" dialects of Mingbulok Kipchak dialects area have 8 vowels due to the fact that the law of synharmonism is fully preserved. Because Beshserka, Qizilqum, Qazokovul, Naiman, Qalgandaryo, Momokhan, Qirqchek, Ingichka, Kichik Jomashuy, Chordona, Uyurchi-Damkol, Kogholikol, Yakkatol, Boston, Guliston, which are part of the Mingbulok dialectal area, Baynalminal, Qairaghochovul, Tolliovul, Oqqum villages are located on the left bank of the Syrdarya stream, and the people living in these areas are representatives of the Kipchak dialect with the "j" ending.

They are the descendants of the herdsman Karakalpak and Naiman clans of the Kazakh and Kyrgyz peoples who settled after the establishment of the Kokan Khanate.

The specific linguistic features of the Kypchak dialects with "J" differ from the literary language in the following cases:

a) y, ch, sh and i sounds are replaced by y and i sounds in most words at the beginning of the word j[ž] is pronounced: žila (yig'la), žür (yur), žänjä//ženjä (yanga), žüjtīp//žüjtīp (shunday qilib), ži:pketti// žiyibketti (chiqib ketdi), žilān (ilon) and b.;

b) in some words, e and a sounds at the beginning of the word ʷekkinchi (ikkinchi), ʷeshki (echki), ʷekki (ikki), ʷajtvär (ayt, aytib yubor) diphthongs like But this phonetic process applies within the framework of a few basic words in this dialectal area, as in other Kipchak-

type dialects, [wöräðä] [wöräðä// wöräðä] ro'za, [wörämäl] ro'mol, [wiriðä] rizo, rozi kabi [3.149] did not take a general shape. However, within sandhi conditions, they are more numerous.

d) the consonant b at the beginning of the word, except for acquisitions, is replaced by p and m: pütün nän (butun non), däjränij mojni (daryoning bo'yi), pojın bo'yin (odamning bo'yni)like.

The position b>m in Turkish words is observed at the beginning of both "y" and "j" group dialect words: mürin (nose is a part of the human body), mürirrāq (**as earlier, earlier**) like.

e) in some cases, the middle y consonant at the beginning of the word is not pronounced : irik (yirik), irin (yiring), iraq (yiroq, uzoq), irtivār (yirtib yubor), iqittin (yiqitting)like.

f) the phenomenon of falling sounds (elision) is observed: yā: (yo'q), pi:lo (piyola), u:lī (o'g'li), tu:rī (to'g'ri), o:ur (og'ir), sāri: (sariq), qāti (qattiq), äčči (achchi)like.

g) It is common to drop the r sound from another language in words: dästixān (dasturxon), binnäsä (bir narsa), čäx, (charx) like.

So, Professor E.D. Polivanov was right when he said: "None of the Turkic languages in the world yet differ between dialects as sharply as the Uzbek language, so none of the Turkic languages have such dialectal diversity" [12.7].

From this point of view, the area of dialects of Mingbulok district has a number of unique features that are observed in some Uzbek dialects, but not in others. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the comparative-historical genesis of the linguistic features of the Uzbek national language and its dialects, which have a colorful and very ancient history, and which have not yet had a purely linguistic study, as well as the area of its spread and application, and classification is the priority content of our work.

Many research works have been carried out on the scientific study of Uzbek folk dialects, their territorial and areal classifications. This work also contributes to filling the general classifications of the Uzbek people and dialects, clarifying and improving some unclear places in them. Mingbulok dialect is a small part of Uzbek dialects.

References:

1. Abdyllov F. Phonetics. - Tashkent: Science, 1967. - P.74-82.
2. Abdyllov U. Ethnolapapo japayonlap in Faggona valley (beginning of XIX-XX asp). - Tashkent: New generation of asp, 2005. - B. 183-200.
3. Bopovkov A.K. O nekotopyx ochepednyx vopposakh uzbekskogo litepatypnogo zytyka. ZIV. AN SSSP, VI. - S. 76
4. Baskakov N.A., Sodikov A., Abdyazizov A. Mymic linguistics. - Tashkent, 1975.
5. Gadjieva N. 3. Ppoblsma tyupkskoy apealnoy lingvistiki. - M.: Naika, 1975. - S. 61-70.
6. Djypaev A.B. Teopeticheskie osnovy apealnogo issledovaniya Uzbekoyazychnogo massiv. - Tashkent: Science, 1991. - B.82.
7. Donyopov H. Shajapa and shevalap of the Uzbek people. - Tashkent: Science, 1968. - P.73.
8. Ibpohimov Y.M. Study of the Uzbek Shevalapi of the Southern Opol. Phil. science dr. ...dis. avtopef. - Tashkent, 2000. - B. 54.

9. Ishaev A. Foneticheskie osobennosti mangitskogo govopa uzbekskogo zhyzika. - Tashkent, 1962. - S. 16.
10. Myhammadjonov Q. South Kazakhstan Uzbek shevalap. - Tashkent, 1981. - B. 14.
11. Nematov H. Tapikh phonetics of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Oqityvchi, 1992.
12. Polivanov E.D. Uzbek dialectology and Uzbek literary language. - Tashkent, 1933. - P.7.
13. Peshetov V.V. Classification of Uzbek dialect // Uzbek language and literature. - Tashkent, 1966. - No. 1. - B. 3-14.
14. Tolstova L. Kapakalpaki Fepganskoy valley. - Nykys, 1959. - S. 27.
15. Shchepbak A. Spavnitelnaya phonetika tyupskikh yazykov. - L., 1970. - S. 37.
16. Epgashev A.A. Apeal-onomastic study of ethnotponymy of Andijan region. Phil. science. name ... diss. avtopef. - Tashkent, 2012. - B. 9

